

Appendix 1 AMIA Diversity, Equity and Inclusion Task Force Charge

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AMIA Diversity, Equity and Inclusion Task Force

The 2020 – 2025 Strategic Plan will be completed by the end of 2020 and will include a continued commitment to growing AMIA as a diverse and inclusive community. Is an organization that is multi-disciplinary and interprofessional as well as diverse in race, ethnicity, nationality, gender, religion, orientation, and ability. The AMIA 2015-2020 strategic plan sets a goal to grow a diverse membership and this will be expanded to reflect more robust efforts in the 2020 – 2025 plan.

The purpose of the Diversity, Equity and Inclusion (DEI) Task Force is to guide and execute strategic goals and objectives related to diversity, equity and inclusion through recommendations to the AMIA Board of Directors. The DEI Task Force directs specific attention to AMIA’s mission and its intersection with systemic racism and health equity.

Diversity, equity and inclusion is a strategic umbrella encompassing multiple concerns including, but not limited to, race, ethnicity, nationality, gender, LGBTQIA+, and ability and initiatives and activities involving affinity groups, S.T.E.M pipeline, program development, education content, leadership development, and mentoring. All are cross-organizational issues affecting AMIA’s individual and organizational membership through governance and staff work in membership, education, meetings, marketing communications, and public policy.

Systemic racism and health equity specifically are a new area of focus for AMIA.

When it comes to informatics science and practice there is a natural intersection with informatics and health disparities – it is the research and practice of investigating the data to inform knowledge that allows for the identification and tracking of disparities in health and healthcare. The impact of health disparities spans the five domains translational bioinformatics, clinical research, consumer, clinical, and public health informatics.

Activism in the systemic racism space necessarily focuses attention on people of African descent with a politicized history reaching back 400 years. The decision to embrace an initiative that is race-specific and may be politicized, especially in an election year is not simple, nor will it be embraced by all members. That is not a reason to reject the idea.

The challenge for the board is to act affirmatively to address the current societal concerns focusing a spotlight on systemic racism as it manifests in the scope of AMIA’s work; while also addressing a longer-term governance concern on diversity, equity and inclusion. This area is far broader than systemic racism focused on African Americans and includes many more constituencies and stakeholders within AMIA organized around race, ethnicity, and gender and the impact on programming and education for pipeline, mentoring and leadership.

While AMIA has had success with the member led Women in AMIA initiative and limited scope for networking, podcast, and pipeline activities, there is little DEI structure to support member engagement beyond Women In AMIA.

AMIA seeks to be a diverse organization, professionally and demographically. While it is not possible to specifically address every area of diversity, equity and inclusion, we strive to assure that the culture, policies, and actions of the organization are equitable and inclusive. Choices must be made and what members need and want is paramount. What we do know is that the 2020-2025 strategic plan must take these concerns into consideration.

The challenge of leading effectively on diversity, equity, and inclusion is dependent on a strong commitment and focus on subject matter and scope. The DEI Task Force will take on this charge.

Responsibilities of the Diversity, Equity and Inclusion Task Force

Scope

Under the 2015-2020 Strategic Plan there are opportunities in 2020 for AMIA to tactically support Diversity, Equity and Inclusion in 3Q and 4Q. However, the role of the task force in advising the 2020-2025 Strategic Plan still in development is of paramount importance.

AMIA staff, in consultation with the chair of the AMIA Board and in coordination with the DEI Task Force, will continue to evaluate ongoing and time-sensitive opportunities related to the 2020 operations.

Reports to Executive Committee monthly and presents at BOD meetings. Formal adjunct to Strategic Planning Task Force.

Operates to move forward swiftly, minimize bureaucracy, easily work across all organizational groups with the imprimatur of the BODs directive.

Stakeholders

Issues related to Diversity, Equity and Inclusion are cross-cutting. The DEITF is expected to define and prioritize key stakeholders within AMIA who need to be engaged in development as well as those impacted by the work externally. Including, but not limited to

- Women in AMIA
- Public Policy Committee/Polymakers
- Health Equity, Global Health and Public Health individual and working group members
- Student members 0 - 9 years, Young Informatics Professionals
- Nominations and Elections committees
- Awards Committee
- Publications Committee
- Membership Committee
- Industry Advisory Committee (IAC)

Task Force Charge

- Construct review of the current Strategic Planning documentation and recommendations as necessary to insure inclusion of the diversity perspective in the work as of June 2020.
- Make recommendations to Strategic Planning Task Force based on review.
- Strengthen pipeline of self-nominated leaders for 2020 election nominations due June 30, 2020.
- Determine course of action for implementing ongoing leader education on **diversity, equity and inclusion**.
- Recommend how to implement specific leader education on racism, systemic racism and health equity including BOD and new leaders taking office in January 2021.
- Recommend a framework to support workforce diversity, exposure to informatics and awareness of AMIA that enable recruitment and retention efforts of students and faculty. (e.g. presentations at conferences, local outreach to college and universities).
- Recommend purpose and methods for member engagement to specifically inform Diversity, Equity and Inclusion Task Force (e.g. listening sessions, online community for Health Equity/Disparities).
- Create a set of DEI principles and a tool (i.e. exploratory questions) to guide AMIA elected and volunteer leaders toward more diversity, equity and inclusion when composing committees, calling volunteers, selecting volunteers, evaluating speakers, and engaging members.
- Develop a presence for activities and/or presented content (minimum late-breaking session) at the AMIA 2020 Annual Symposium.

- Make recommendations for activities and/or presented content for each AMIA meeting Summit, Clinical Informatics Conference, Academic Forum meeting, Policy Forum.
- Conduct environmental scan and report of DEI activities in similar associations and societies for future task force/committee review.
- Consider tactical recommendations which require immediate 3Q/4Q 2020 planning.

(For example: is there a role for the Journals that needs planning in June/July 2020 in order to show up in 2021 content; is there content planning for the 2020 Annual Symposium that requires planning with the Scientific Program Committee and HQ staff.

- Envision that a permanent committee for **AMIA Diversity, Equity and Inclusion** will be created following the Task Force term to provide ongoing guidance and policy recommendations to the AMIA Board.
- Apprise the Board of other questions and issues needing the Board's attention and decision.
- Work with AMIA HQ Marcom staff to develop ongoing messaging

Term

Twelve months term.

BOD reviews for extension of Task Force term or establishment of permanent Committee status and directives.

Reporting

The Task Force reports to the AMIA Executive Committee and reports at the Board meeting as needed or requested.

Membership

To exercise its evaluative functions the DEI Task Force will have access to membership data. Each member of the Task Force will abide by *AMIA's Conflict of Interest Policy* and will not disseminate any proprietary confidential information.

The DEI Task Force and any additional invited or appointed volunteers will have a composition that is

- Varied in activity and engagement in AMIA
- Demonstrates interest in the membership experience and volunteerism (e.g. participation in working groups or leadership, meeting attendance, submission or presentation, reviewer status, journal submission, etc.)

AND/OR

- Active AMIA member status and demonstrated volunteer experience in diversity, equity and inclusion efforts for another organization (e.g. employer, institution, association or society)
- Varied in race, ethnicity, gender, orientation, age, religion, ability, geography, nationality
- Varied in member type, informatics domain and inclusive of research and practice informaticians
- Brings new voices to the table

Leader

- Tiffani Bright, Chair and Board Member

Potential Members

Tiffani worked with AMIA to balance gender, ethnicity/race; additional identity diversity; roles; industry and job/geography and to have two individuals represent each diversity component.

Suzanne Bakken, PhD, RN, FAAN, FACMI
Casey Overby-Taylor, PhD
Karen Wang, MD MHS
Rosemary Ventura, DNP, RN-BC
Carolyn Petersen, MS, MBI, FAMIA
Rubina F. Rizvi, MD, PhD
Oliver J. Bear Don't Walk IV, MS
Jyotishman Pathak, Ph.D., FACMI
Carl Johnson, MD, EdM, MS
David Butler, MD
Clair Kronk, BSc.
Kevin B. Johnson, MD, MS

Ex-officio members without vote include

- AMIA Board Chair (Patti Dykes)
- AMIA President and CEO (TBD)
- AMIA Executive Vice President and COO (Karen Greenwood)

Staff Liaison

The DEI works across the organization and cross departmentally to engage membership, meetings, education, governance/operations and public policy. There is a heavy communications component to the DEI Task Force work and will be supported with marketing and communications staff at HQ. They will coordinate additional staff support as needed depending on DEI Task Force activities.

- VP Marketing and Communications (Krista Martin)
- Director, Public Relations and Marketing (Lisa Gibson)